

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. **B435**
Date: 14 Apr 2009
Take Off: 08:53:08Z 12:26:32Z 16:13:00Z
Landing: 09:42:32Z 14:59:40Z 16:54:51Z
Flight Time: 0h 49m 32s 2h 33m 08s 0h 41m 51s

Campaign: MEVEX Test flight

Operating Area: Area Alpha/Bravo

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Al Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Dave Pollard	Met Office ** Cranfield-Exeter ONLY **	
5	Flight Manager 1/ AVAPS	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Test / Flight Manager 2	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics 1 / Chemistry	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics 2	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SID3 1	Richard Greenaway	University of Hertfordshire	
10	Ops	Peter Chappell	Directflight	
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
ViRC chat log	No log available / ViRC not used
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
SID3	SID3 operator does not create a log sheet?
AVAPS	Log not available so far

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

no data on BADC 30 Dec 2009

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B435
 Date: 14 April 2009
 Project: Mevex - shakedown flight
 Location: Western approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
084811		!	0.44 kft	128	start taxi
085017		!	0.45 kft	177	ASPs opened
085416		T/O	1.9 kft	038	085308
091940		!	10.0 kft	224	Nez zero
094958		Land	0.24 kft	131	094232
095421		!	0.24 kft	131	at Exeter
122059		!	0.23 kft	130	start taxi
122944		T/O	5.7 kft	274	EGTE @ 122632
123350		!	10.0 kft	263	enter cloud
123822		nev	10.0 kft	267	zero
123928		heimann	10.0 kft	248	cal 07
124316		!	10.0 kft	231	transit
125618		video	10.0 kft	228	recording spotter as UFC
125807	130342	Run 1	10.0 kft	200	n>s
130056		!	10.0 kft	181	abeam fraggle rock
130645	131027	Run 2	5.0 kft	007	
130756		!	5.0 kft	002	abeam
131233	131823	Run 3	3.3 - 3.2 kft	151	
131520		abeam	3.3 kft	179	
131937		!	1.8 kft	209	video now spotter only @ 25fps
132000		!	1.5 kft	151	video previous run - @ 5fps
132446		!	1.2 kft	039	abeam
132711		!	1.2 kft	355	run 4 start missed
132755		!	1.2 kft	345	end run 4
132907	133615	Run n5	0.75 - 0.73 kft	178	
133301		!	0.62 kft	151	abeam
133839	133927	Profile 1	0.42 - 0.28 kft	346	
133920		!	0.24 kft	347	50ft
133935	134734	Run 6	0.29 - 0.34 kft	346	
134042		Heimann	0.31 kft	347	cal06
135035		orbit 1	0.73 kft	221	
135100		!	0.75 kft	011	250M start
135145		end orbit 1	0.68 kft	243	
135328	140141	Run 7	3.2 kft	161	
135949		!	3.2 kft	158	abeam - good spotter
140151		climb	3.4 kft	161	
142123	143140	Run 8	30.0 kft	174	
142624		sonde 1	30.0 kft	196	
143229		descend	30.0 kft	104	to Exeter
150102		!	0.24 kft	189	land Exeter 14:59:40
161618		T/O exeter	5.0 kft	000	16:13:00
165602		land	0.46 kft	357	16:54:51 cranfield

Analysis chart
Valid 0000 UTC Tue 14 Apr 2009

B435 07:08:32-16:58:01

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

MEVEX Test flight – Sortie – B435

Date: 14th April 2009

Sector 1:

T/O EGTC: 10:00L

Land EGTE: 11:00L

Sector 2:

T/O EGTE: 13:00L

Land EGTE: 16:00L

Sector 3:

T/O EGTE: 17:00L

Land EGTC: 18:00L

Location: Area Alpha/Bravo

Weather: Ideally clear skies and BL aerosol

Sortie Aim: To test key instrumentation for the MEVEX campaign

Key Instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, SID 3, AVAPS, Nephs

Sortie profile:

1. Take off EGTC and position to EGTE with core instruments and cloud physics running, if conditions are conducive to testing SID3, this will be done in cloud, if possible, at science cruise, otherwise high speed transit [60 mins, 60 Total for Sector 1]
2. Take off EGTE and transit to operating area at appropriate level (~FL100) [25 mins, 25 Total]
3. SLR at 10 kft passing 4.353 km to right of a suitable surface target in order to image target with IR cameras [5 mins, 30 Total]
4. Descend in turn and SLR at 5 kft passing 2.176 km to right of target [10 mins, 40 Total]
5. Descend in turn and SLR at 3 kft passing 1.306 km to right of target [10 mins, 50 Total]
6. Descend in turn and SLR at 1 kft passing 435 m to right of target [10 mins, 60 Total]
7. Descend in turn and SLR at 500 ft passing 218 m to right of target [10 mins, 70 Total]
8. Profile descent to 50 ft [1 min, 71 Total]
9. SLR at 100 ft [15 mins, 86 Total]
10. Perform an Orbit at angle of bank to be determined by aircraft scientist [5 mins, 91 Total]
11. Profile ascent to level ~2 kft above boundary layer aerosol [9 mins, 100 Total]
12. SLR ~2kft above boundary layer aerosol [10 mins, 110 Total]
13. Profile ascent to high level [20 mins, 130 Total]
14. SLR at high level (~FL300) dropping a sonde at midpoint [10 mins, 140 Total]
15. CONTINGENCY TIME (this may be used to repeat a surface target run in the event of a 'miss', or to investigate mixed phase or cirrus cloud if any is encountered on the profile ascent) [15 mins, 155 Total]
16. Recover to EGTE [25 mins, 180 Total for sector 2]
17. Reposition to EGTC [60 mins Total for sector 3]

Specific Instrument requirements:

- ARIES – Nadir views from high level if clear skies, 50/50 Nadir and zenith during low level work, follow SWS in orbits
- Nephs – Attempt to vary flow rate to achieve differing cyclone impactor cuts during runs in BL aerosol (anticipating only sea salt)
- IIR – obtain images of surface target, calibration unimportant
- SWS point mainly at aerosol (or cirrus) layer

Flight:

B435

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

ARIES flight log

Flight: **B435**

page 1 of 1

Date: **14/APR/09** Operator(s): **S. Rogers**

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: **Pre-MEVEX test Roll - SW Approaches**

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
09 58			CH	C	71	20	CH cal.
11 29	Takeoff						
11 43 30	Transit		CH	C	71	22	CH cal. C might still be cooling from over-temperature on the ground. 11:51 CBB = 22°C so stable.
11 58 07	FL100	N/Z long	NZ	O	70	22	NZ long. Altitude N&Z with interleaved CH
12 04 13	↓	CH cal	CH	O	70	22	CH cal Oups - didn't stop previous scan properly.
12 06 30			CH	O	71	21	CH cal.
12 07 50	5000ft	N/Z long	NZ	O	70	22	NZ long 30 sec { start in
12 11 45	↓ 3000ft	NZ long	NZ	O	71	22	NZ long 30 sec { turn/descent.
12 19 40	↓ 1000ft	NZ long	NZ	O	71	23	NZ long 30 sec CH N CH Z CH....
12 25 40	↓ 500ft	NZ long	NZ	O	71	23	NZ long 30 sec (timing?)
12 36 45	↓ 500ft/1000ft	NZ long	NZ	O	70	23	NZ long 12 28 turn/descent.
12 48 00	↑	CH cal	CH	O	71	23	CH cal.
12 50 28	↓ 500ft	Z	Z	O	70	23	Zenith 1x n ^{!!!} CH orbit (start at roll)
12 52 00		CH cal	CH	O	71	23	CH cal.
12 53 41	3000ft	NZ long	NZ	O	71	23	NZ long 30s.
13 15 30	↑ FL300?	CH cal	CH	O	71	22	CH cal.
13 17 00		CH cal	CH	O	71	22	CH cal.
13 18 -		480 x 1	N	O	71	23	Nadir.
13 22 37		N3 min	N	O	71	21	Nadir 3 min + CH
13 28 40		Z3 min	Z	O	70	22	Zenith 3 min
13 31 55		CH cal	CH	O	71	22	CH cal.